

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: September 17, 2024

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

医中誌

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P ***Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).***

I ***Oral intake of lycopene***

C ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***

O ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***

S ***Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies***

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 Lycopene/TH or リコピン/AL or Lycopene/AL or リコペン/AL or ψ -カロテン/AL or プサイカロテン/AL or psi カロテン/AL or ψ -Carotene/AL or psi-Carotene/AL or LYC-O-MATO/AL or LYCOMATO/AL or "LYC O MATO"/AL or ATERONON/AL or "BLAKESLEA TRISPORA"/AL or "CI 75125"/AL or CI-75125/AL or CI75125/AL or "E 160D"/AL or E-160D/AL or E160D/AL or LYCORED/AL or "MEXORYL SAQ"/AL or MEXORYL-SAQ/AL or "NSC 407322"/AL or NSC-407322/AL or NSC407322/AL or

REDIVIVO/AL or SOLANORUBIN/AL or "TOMAT O RED"/AL or TOMAT-O-RED/AL or 502-65-8/AL or 13018-46-7/AL 401
#2 "LDL Cholesterol"/TH or LDL-C/AL or LDLC/AL or ((LDL/AL or "Low Density Lipoprotein"/AL or "Beta
Lipoprotein"/AL or Beta-Lipoprotein/AL or 低比重リポタンパク/AL or 低比重リポ蛋白/AL or 低比重リポたんぱく/AL or 低密度リ
ポタンパク/AL or 低密度リポ蛋白/AL or 低密度リポたんぱく/AL or "Low-Density Lipoprotein"/AL or Low-Density-
Lipoprotein/AL or 悪玉/AL) and (Cholesterol/AL or コレステロール/AL)) 17,028
#3 #1 and #2 4

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 24, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

1 以下を OR で加えてはいかがでしょうか。

トマト/TH OR トマト/TA OR スイカ属/TH OR スイカ/TA

2

LDL とコレステロールの掛け合わせ（AND 検索）ではなく、全て OR 検索としてはいかがでしょうか。ご検討ください。また、Pubmed と合わせて脂質関連も検索に含めるようご検討ください（例：脂質/TH or 脂質/AL or 脂肪/AL or 高脂/AL）

論文種類原著論文+総説に絞り込んではいかがでしょうか。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/presspeer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 非顯示

Email: 非顯示

Date submitted: August 30, 2024 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

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My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** *Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).*
- I** *Oral intake of lycopene*
- C** *Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention*
- O** *Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)*
- S** *Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies*

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 *"lycopene"[Supplementary Concept] OR "lycopene"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopene**"[All Fields] 6,821*
#2 *"plants"[MeSH Terms] OR "vegetables"[MeSH Terms] OR "vegetable**"[All Fields] OR "fruit"[MeSH Terms] OR "fruit**"[All Fields] OR "solanum lycopersicum"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopersicon esculentum"[All Fields] OR "tomato**"[All Fields] OR "citrullus"[MeSH Terms] OR "watermelon**"[All Fields] OR "water melon**"[All Fields] 585,715*

#3 "dietary supplements"[MeSH Terms] OR "supplement*"[Title/Abstract] 492,222
#4 #1 AND (#2 OR #3) 3,625
#5 "randomized controlled trial"[Publication Type] OR "controlled clinical trial"[Publication Type] OR
"randomized"[Title/Abstract] OR "placebo"[Title/Abstract] OR "clinical trials as topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR
"randomly"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial"[Title] 1,636,448
#6 "case control studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "control groups"[MeSH Terms] OR ("case*"[Title/Abstract] AND
"control*"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("case*"[Title/Abstract] AND "comparison*"[Title/Abstract]) OR "control
group*"[Title/Abstract] OR "cohort studies"[MeSH Terms] OR "cohort"[Title/Abstract] OR "longitudinal"[Title/Abstract] OR
"prospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "retrospective"[Title/Abstract] OR "cross sectional studies"[MeSH Terms] OR
"crosssectional"[Title/Abstract] OR "transversal stud*"[Title/Abstract] 5,216,816
#7 #5 OR #6 6,271,382
#8 #7 NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms]) 5,926,890
#9 #4 AND #8 862
#10 "cholesterol, ldl"[MeSH Terms] OR "low density lipoprotein"[Title/Abstract] OR "cholesterol"[MeSH Terms] OR
"cholesterol"[Title/Abstract] OR "lipids"[MeSH Terms] OR "lipid*"[Title/Abstract] 1,732,907
#11 #9 AND #10 256

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 12, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example: "cholesterol, Idl"[MeSH Terms] は、"cholesterol"[MeSH Terms]の下位語のため、検索に含めなくても同件数の結果となります。

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 4. Text word searching | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. Limits and filters | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Overall evaluation | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

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<https://www.cadth.ca/presspeer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

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Searcher: 非顯示

Email: 非顯示

Date submitted: August 30, 2024 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

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This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library/Wiley

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P ***Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).***

I ***Oral intake of lycopene***

C ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***

O ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***

S ***Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies***

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 ***(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene"):ti,ab,kw 769***
#2 ***MeSH descriptor: [Lycopene] explode all trees 319***

#3 #1 OR #2 769
#4 MeSH descriptor: [Plants] explode all trees 3,983
#5 MeSH descriptor: [Vegetables] explode all trees 2,495
#6 MeSH descriptor: [Fruit] explode all trees 3,652
#7 MeSH descriptor: [Solanum lycopersicum] explode all trees 151
#8 MeSH descriptor: [Citrullus] explode all trees 39
#9 ("tomato" OR "tomatoes" OR "solanum lycopersicum" OR "lycopersicon esculentum" OR "citrullus" OR "watermelon" OR "water melon"):ti,ab,kw 851
#10 MeSH descriptor: [Dietary Supplements] explode all trees 20,293
#11 #3 AND (#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10) 464
#12 (randomized controlled trial OR controlled clinical trial):pt OR (randomized OR placebo OR randomly):ti,ab,kw OR (trial):ti 1,469,402
#13 MeSH descriptor: [Case-Control Studies] explode all trees 29,602
#14 MeSH descriptor: [Control Groups] explode all trees 335
#15 MeSH descriptor: [Cohort Studies] explode all trees 212,151
#16 MeSH descriptor: [Cross-Sectional Studies] explode all trees 9,937
#17 #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 1,516,919
#18 #11 AND #17 380
#19 MeSH descriptor: [Cholesterol, LDL] explode all trees 6,233
#20 MeSH descriptor: [Cholesterol] explode all trees 13,132
#21 MeSH descriptor: [Lipids] explode all trees 64,651
#22 ("low-density lipoprotein"):ti,ab,kw OR (cholesterol):ti,ab,kw OR (lipid):ti,ab,kw OR (LDL):ti,ab,kw 74,287
#23 #18 AND #22 122

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 12, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example: #19・・・#20 の下位語のため、検索に含めなくても同件数になります

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

#10・・・PubMed に合わせて、(supplement*):ti,ab,kw も検索に含めるとよいかと思ひます。

#22...lipid→lipid*

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

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Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

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6. Limits and filters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Cochrane Library で検索する CENTRAL は、RCT のみ収録されているデータベースのため、研究デザインの語による絞込みは行いません。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

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(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

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(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

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(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

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- C** ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***
- O** ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***
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Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 ALL((lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene")) AND ALL ("randomized controlled trial" OR

"controlled clinical trial" OR "randomized" OR "placebo" OR "randomly" OR "trial" OR "cohort" OR "case-control" OR "cross-sectional") 26

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 19, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Mesh の使用を推奨します。(mh: ~)

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

研究デザインでの絞込みについて、次のページに式の例を示しました。ご確認ください。

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. Limits and filters | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Overall evaluation | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

例 : ((lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") OR (mh:"lycopene")) AND (((random* OR trial* OR placebo OR cohort OR case-control* OR cross-section*)) OR (mh:("Clinical Study" OR "Clinical Trial" OR "Randomized Controlled Trial" OR "Controlled Clinical Trial" OR "Epidemiologic Studies" OR "Case-Control Studies" OR "Cohort Studies" OR "Cross-Sectional Studies")))

→83 件になるでしょうか。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

- Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/presspeer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 非開示 Email: 非開示

Date submitted: August 30, 2024 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ICTRP

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

ICTRP

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P ***Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).***

I ***Oral intake of lycopene***

C ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***

O ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***

S ***Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies***

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 ***(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Title :Recruitment status is ALL 106 records for 104 trials***
#2 ***(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR***

**"Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO"
OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Intervention :Recruitment status is ALL 132 records for 130 trials
#3 #1 OR #2 132 records for 130 trials**

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 12, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.")

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. Limits and filters | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Overall evaluation | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

- Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

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Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 非顯示

Email: 非顯示

Date submitted: August 30, 2024 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P ***Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).***

I ***Oral intake of lycopene***

C ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***

O ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***

S ***Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies***

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Other terms 116

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: September 24, 2024

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

(lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "Alltrans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Intervention/treatment 83 件

念のため「Intervention/treatment」フィールドでも同じ検索語での検索記録を一応入れていただくとより丁寧かもしれません。ですが、上記の 83 件は「in Other terms」116 件に全て含まれていたため、無くても支障はございません。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/presspeer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 非顯示

Email: 非顯示

Date submitted: August 30, 2024 Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on LDL-cholesterol

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene reduce blood LDL-C levels compared to oral intake of a test substance that does not contain lycopene?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** ***Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).***
- I** ***Oral intake of lycopene***
- C** ***Oral intake of test product without lycopene or without any intervention***
- O** ***Blood LDL-C levels(no secondary outcome will be defined.)***
- S** ***Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, cohort studies, case-control studies***

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]** Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1	リコピン	19
#2	リコペン	8
#3	プロリコピン	0
#4	ライコマート	0
#5	lycopene	25

#6	<i>prolycopene</i>	0
#7	<i>LYC-O-MATO</i>	0
#8	<i>All-trans-lycopene</i>	0
#9	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 28	

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 非開示

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2024/09/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- | | | | |
|---------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. Limits and filters | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Overall evaluation | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan.

<https://www.cadth.ca/presspeer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>